

Notes on the Weyl tensor, decomposition of Riemann tensor, Ruse-Lanczos identity and duality of the curvature tensor

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Abstract

These notes have the pedagogical purpose of exposing mathematical accounts about of the Weyl tensor. The development of calculations is presented to obtain the curvature tensor from the conformal transformation, consequently resulting in the Weyl conformal tensor and the Riemann tensor reveals itself decomposed into its parts. The Ruse-Lanczos identity is a useful mathematical tool to build duality identities in the two pairs of antisymmetric indices of the Riemann tensor components.

Keywords: Weyl tensor, decomposition of the Riemann tensor, dual tensor

1. Introduction

In accordance with tensorial approach of the Electromagnetic Theory, the electromagnetic field is given in terms of the four-vector $F_\mu = E_\mu + iB_\mu$, where $E_\mu = (0, E_1, E_2, E_3)$ and $B_\mu = (0, B_1, B_2, B_3)$ are electric and magnetic field observed by an observer in an inertial reference frame, where the four-velocity vector of the observer is a timelike vector $u^\mu = (1, 0, 0, 0)$. Thus, the four-electromagnetic vector is given by $F_\mu = F_{\mu\nu}u^\nu + i\tilde{F}_{\mu\nu}u^\nu$, where the $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the field-strength tensor of electromagnetism and the $\tilde{F}_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2}\epsilon_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}F^{\kappa\lambda}$ is its dual field-strength tensor. In this formalism, we separate the electric vector given by $E_\mu = F_{\mu\nu}u^\nu$ and magnetic vector given by $B_\mu = \tilde{F}_{\mu\nu}u^\nu$ with aid of dual operation. In fact, in the inertial reference frame in which it is at rest, the vectors E_μ and B_μ , are spatial three-vectors, then we can put $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{E} + i\mathbf{B}$, where the six components of the field-strength tensor of electromagnetism $F_{\mu\nu}$ are into complex three-vector \mathbf{F} [1]. The duality of an antisymmetric tensor like field-strength tensor of electromagnetism can be used for split vectorial components. With this in mind we can apply the dual operation to the pair of antisymmetric indices of Riemann curvature tensor. In the literature that deals with duality of the Riemann curvature tensor, decomposed into its irreducible components, the Weyl tensor, the Ricci tensor and the curvature scalar, seldom makes explicit details of calculations involving the decomposition of the the Riemann curvature tensor. In the basic courses of General Relativity, presents Weyl tensor as a definition without exposing the details of the calculations that lead to it. Some books, for example [2, 3], present the conformal transformation and indicate the path to be followed to obtain the Weyl curvature tensor. In this paper we solved this exercise to obtain the Weyl tensor from conformal transformation and explained the decomposition of Riemann curvature tensor. In order to obtain the duality properties of Riemann curvature tensor, it is necessary to study the Ruse-Lanczos identity [4]. Consequently, in the same way as for the duality of electromagnetismo we present the formalism of duality and complexification of the parts of Riemann curvature tensor.

According to General Relativity, the Riemann curvature tensor, $R^\kappa{}_{\mu\lambda\nu}$, is related to the distribution of matter, specifically by Ricci tensor, $R_{\mu\nu} = R^\kappa{}_{\mu\kappa\nu}$, directly related to the local energy-momentum tensor by Einstein's field equations,

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}, \quad (1)$$

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where G is the gravitational Newton's constant and we are overlooking the value of the cosmological constant. In free gravitational field, we have no matter, $T_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and consequently we have null Ricci tensor, $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$. Greek labels refer to four dimensional spacetime and we use metric signature $(-+++)$.

2. Conformal transformation

Hermann Weyl tried to unify electromagnetism and gravitation, this attempt was carried out in 1919 [5], however this attempt failed, but Weyl introduced a new principle of invariance in his theory, a scale change of the metric tensor given by $\bar{g} = e^{2\omega} g$. This principle later evolved through Quantum Field Theory being known as 'gauge invariance' [6, 7, 8]. A scale change of the metric tensor is classified as conformal transformation in Riemannian Geometry leading to the Weyl conformal tensor.

Let (\mathcal{M}, g) be a spacetime where \mathcal{M} is pseudo-Riemannian manifold and g is a Lorentz metric tensor. A conformal transformation [2, 3, 9] is not a change of coordinates but an actual change in the geometry under a 'gauge transformation' [10] as already mentioned,

$$\bar{g} = e^{2\omega} g, \quad (2)$$

where g e \bar{g} are metric tensors on the manifold \mathcal{M} and $\omega = \omega(x)$ is a real function of the spacetime coordinates. The 'gauge transformation' in equation (2) is a rescaling of the metric tensor and it is named Weyl rescaling.

In the Weyl rescaling we can state that \bar{g} is conformally related to g , because the gauge transformation (2) preserves the angle between two vectors U and V of the tangent space $T_p(\mathcal{M})$. The inner product between the two vectors U and V , denoted by $U \cdot V = g(U, V)$ and the measure of the angle between two vectors follows from the definition,

$$\cos \theta = \frac{U \cdot V}{|U||V|} = \frac{g(U, V)}{\sqrt{g(U, U)} \sqrt{g(V, V)}}. \quad (3)$$

The measure of the angle between the same two vectors under Weyl rescaling (2) is given by,

$$\cos \bar{\theta} = \frac{\bar{g}(U, V)}{\sqrt{\bar{g}(U, U)} \sqrt{\bar{g}(V, V)}} = \frac{e^{2\omega} g(U, V)}{\sqrt{e^{2\omega} g(U, U)} \sqrt{e^{2\omega} g(V, V)}} = \frac{g(U, V)}{\sqrt{g(U, U)} \sqrt{g(V, V)}} = \cos \theta, \quad (4)$$

therefore comparing the equation (3) and (4), the Weyl rescaling is a conformal transformation that preserves the angle but changes the scale. In accordance with this statement, a conformal transformation on spacetime (\mathcal{M}, g) preserves the local light cone structure, where, timelike vectors remain timelike vectors, spacelike vectors remain spacelike vectors and null vectors remain null vectors. A very useful applications are the Penrose conformal diagrams that enable the whole of an infinite spacetime to be represented as a finite diagram, by applying a conformal transformation to the metric structure [9, 11].

2.1. Calculation of the connections or Christoffel symbols and Riemann curvature tensor in a conformal space

Let us compute the Riemann curvature tensor and for the first step, we calculate the Christoffel symbols in a conformal space starting with

$$\bar{\Gamma}^{\rho}_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \bar{g}^{\rho\sigma} (\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + \bar{g}_{\nu\sigma,\mu} - \bar{g}_{\mu\nu,\sigma}). \quad (5)$$

with a comma denoting a partial derivative. To facilitate some calculations let us admit that $e^{\omega(x)} \rightarrow \Omega(x)$ is some non-vanishing scalar function of position in the Weyl local rescaling metric of the metric tensor (2),

$$\bar{g}_{\mu\nu} = \Omega^2 g_{\mu\nu} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{g}^{\mu\nu} = \Omega^{-2} g^{\mu\nu}, \quad (6)$$

replacing above equation (6) into Christoffel symbols $\bar{\Gamma}^{\rho}_{\mu\nu}$ and calculating the derivatives, we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Gamma}^{\rho}_{\mu\nu} &= \frac{1}{2} \Omega^{-2} g^{\rho\sigma} [2\Omega(\Omega_{,\nu})g_{\mu\sigma} + \Omega^2 g_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + 2\Omega(\Omega_{,\mu})g_{\nu\sigma} + \Omega^2 g_{\nu\sigma,\mu} - 2\Omega(\Omega_{,\sigma})g_{\mu\nu} - \Omega^2 g_{\mu\nu,\sigma}] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \Omega^{-2} g^{\rho\sigma} [\Omega^2 (g_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + g_{\nu\sigma,\mu} - g_{\mu\nu,\sigma})] + \frac{1}{2} \Omega^{-2} g^{\rho\sigma} [2\Omega(\Omega_{,\nu})g_{\mu\sigma} + \Omega_{,\mu} g_{\nu\sigma} - \Omega_{,\sigma} g_{\mu\nu}], \end{aligned}$$

that is

$$\bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\mu\nu} = \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\nu} + \Omega^{-1}(\delta^\rho_\mu \Omega_{,\nu} + \delta^\rho_\nu \Omega_{,\mu} - g^{\rho\sigma} g_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma}). \quad (7)$$

Now we can calculate the Riemann curvature tensor in a conformal space with metric tensor \bar{g} ,

$$\bar{R}^\rho_{\mu\sigma\nu} = \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + \bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} - \bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\sigma\mu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\nu\kappa} \quad (8)$$

where we need to calculate the derivative of Christoffel symbol (7), that it will result in the first term of Riemann curvature tensor (8),

$$\bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\mu\nu,\sigma} = \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\nu,\sigma} + \delta^\rho_\mu (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\nu})_{,\sigma} + \delta^\rho_\nu (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\mu})_{,\sigma} - g_{\mu\nu,\sigma} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa}) - g_{\mu\nu} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\sigma}.$$

The second term of Riemann curvature tensor (8) is similar to the above first term, for just changing the indexes $\nu \leftrightarrow \sigma$,

$$\bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\mu\sigma,\nu} = \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + \delta^\rho_\mu (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\sigma})_{,\nu} + \delta^\rho_\sigma (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\mu})_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\sigma,\nu} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa}) - g_{\mu\sigma} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\nu}.$$

By subtracting the two terms above, we have that,

$$\delta^\rho_\mu (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\nu})_{,\sigma} - \delta^\rho_\mu (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\sigma})_{,\nu} = \delta^\rho_\mu [(-\Omega^{-2} \Omega_{,\sigma} \Omega_{,\nu} + \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\nu\sigma}) - (-\Omega^{-2} \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma} + \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\sigma\nu})] = 0$$

and then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\mu\sigma,\nu} &= \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + \delta^\rho_\nu (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\mu})_{,\sigma} - \delta^\rho_\sigma (\Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\mu})_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu,\sigma} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa}) + g_{\mu\sigma,\nu} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa}) \\ &\quad + g_{\mu\sigma} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu} (g^{\rho\kappa} \Omega^{-1} \Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\sigma}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Let us calculate the third term of Riemann curvature tensor of equation (8),

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} &= [\Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} + \Omega^{-1}(\delta^\kappa_\mu \Omega_{,\nu} + \delta^\kappa_\nu \Omega_{,\mu} - g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda})][\Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} + \Omega^{-1}(\delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\kappa} + \delta^\rho_\kappa \Omega_{,\sigma} - g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda})] \\ &= \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} + \Omega^{-1}(\delta^\kappa_\mu \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\nu} + \delta^\kappa_\nu \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\mu} - \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda}) \\ &\quad + \Omega^{-1}(\delta^\rho_\sigma \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\kappa} + \delta^\rho_\kappa \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma} - \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda}) \\ &\quad + \Omega^{-2}(\delta^\kappa_\mu \delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\kappa} + \delta^\kappa_\nu \delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\sigma} - \delta^\kappa_\mu g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda} \\ &\quad + \delta^\kappa_\nu \delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\kappa} + \delta^\kappa_\nu \delta^\rho_\kappa \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\sigma} - \delta^\kappa_\nu g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\lambda} \\ &\quad - g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \delta^\rho_\kappa \Omega_{,\sigma} \Omega_{,\lambda} + g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\tau} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda} \Omega_{,\tau}), \end{aligned}$$

the last term in above equation can be simplified,

$$g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\tau} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda} \Omega_{,\tau} = \delta^\lambda_\sigma g_{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\tau} \Omega_{,\lambda} \Omega_{,\tau} = g_{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\tau} \Omega_{,\sigma} \Omega_{,\tau}.$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} &= \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} + \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\mu} \Omega_{,\nu} + \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\nu} \Omega_{,\mu} + \delta^\rho_\sigma \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\kappa} + \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma} - g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda}) \\ &\quad + \Omega^{-2}(\delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\mu} + \delta^\rho_\mu \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma} + \delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\mu} + \delta^\rho_\nu \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\sigma} - g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\mu\sigma} \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\sigma\nu} \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\lambda} \\ &\quad - g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma} \Omega_{,\lambda} + g_{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\lambda} \Omega_{,\sigma} \Omega_{,\lambda}), \end{aligned}$$

we can see that the last two terms cancel each other resulting in

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} &= \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} + \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\mu} \Omega_{,\nu} + \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\nu} \Omega_{,\mu} + \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma} + \delta^\rho_\sigma \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\kappa} - g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\nu} \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\sigma\kappa} \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda}) \\ &\quad + \Omega^{-2}[2\delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\nu} + \delta^\rho_\mu \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\sigma} + \delta^\rho_\nu \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\sigma} - g^{\rho\lambda} (g_{\mu\sigma} \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g_{\nu\sigma} \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\lambda}) - g_{\mu\nu} \delta^\rho_\sigma g^{\kappa\lambda} \Omega_{,\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda}] \end{aligned}$$

The fourth and final term of Riemann curvature tensor of equation (8), is similar to the above third term, for just changing the indexes $\nu \leftrightarrow \sigma$,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\sigma\mu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\nu\kappa} &= \Gamma^\kappa_{\sigma\mu} \Gamma^\rho_{\nu\kappa} + \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma^\rho_{\nu\mu} \Omega_{,\sigma} + \Gamma^\rho_{\nu\sigma} \Omega_{,\mu} + \Gamma^\rho_{\mu\sigma} \Omega_{,\nu} + \delta^\rho_\nu \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\sigma} \Omega_{,\kappa} - g^{\kappa\lambda} g_{\mu\sigma} \Gamma^\rho_{\nu\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g^{\rho\lambda} g_{\nu\kappa} \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\sigma} \Omega_{,\lambda}) \\ &\quad + \Omega^{-2}[2\delta^\rho_\nu \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\sigma} + \delta^\rho_\mu \Omega_{,\sigma} \Omega_{,\nu} + \delta^\rho_\sigma \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\nu} - g^{\rho\lambda} (g_{\mu\sigma} \Omega_{,\nu} \Omega_{,\lambda} - g_{\sigma\nu} \Omega_{,\mu} \Omega_{,\lambda}) - g_{\mu\sigma} \delta^\rho_\nu g^{\kappa\lambda} \Omega_{,\kappa} \Omega_{,\lambda}]. \end{aligned}$$

The subtraction between the third and the fourth terms obtained above results in,

$$\bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} - \bar{\Gamma}^\kappa_{\sigma\mu} \bar{\Gamma}^\rho_{\nu\kappa} = \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} - \Gamma^\kappa_{\sigma\mu} \Gamma^\rho_{\nu\kappa} + \Omega^{-1}[(\delta^\rho_\sigma \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\nu} - \delta^\rho_\nu \Gamma^\kappa_{\mu\sigma}) \Omega_{,\kappa} - g^{\kappa\lambda} (g_{\mu\nu} \Gamma^\rho_{\sigma\kappa} - g_{\mu\sigma} \Gamma^\rho_{\nu\kappa}) \Omega_{,\lambda}]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -g^{\rho\lambda}(g_{\sigma\kappa}\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\kappa} - g_{\nu\kappa}\Gamma_{\mu\sigma}^{\kappa})\Omega_{,\lambda}] + \Omega^{-2}[(\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\Omega_{,\nu} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\Omega_{,\sigma})\Omega_{,\mu} - g^{\rho\kappa}(g_{\mu\sigma}\Omega_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\sigma})\Omega_{,\kappa}] \\
& -g^{\kappa\lambda}(g_{\mu\nu}\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma}\delta^{\rho}_{\nu})\Omega_{,\kappa}\Omega_{,\lambda}]. \tag{10}
\end{aligned}$$

So, composing the Riemann curvature tensor (8),

$$\bar{R}^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu} = \bar{\Gamma}^{\rho}_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - \bar{\Gamma}^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + \bar{\Gamma}^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu}\bar{\Gamma}^{\rho}_{\sigma\kappa} - \bar{\Gamma}^{\kappa}_{\sigma\mu}\bar{\Gamma}^{\rho}_{\nu\kappa},$$

by adding the terms obtained with the equations (9) and (10) that are part of the the Riemann tensor,

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{R}^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu} = & \Gamma^{\rho}_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - \Gamma^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma,\nu} + \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu})_{,\sigma} - \delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu})_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu,\sigma}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + g_{\mu\sigma,\nu}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) \\
& + g_{\mu\sigma}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\sigma} + \Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\sigma\kappa} - \Gamma^{\kappa}_{\sigma\mu}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\nu\kappa} \\
& + \Omega^{-1}[(\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\sigma})\Omega_{,\kappa} - g^{\kappa\lambda}(g_{\mu\nu}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\sigma\kappa} - g_{\mu\sigma}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\nu\kappa})\Omega_{,\lambda} - g^{\rho\lambda}(g_{\sigma\kappa}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu} - g_{\nu\kappa}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\sigma})\Omega_{,\lambda}] \\
& + \Omega^{-2}[(\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\Omega_{,\nu} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\Omega_{,\sigma})\Omega_{,\mu} - g^{\rho\kappa}(g_{\mu\sigma}\Omega_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\sigma})\Omega_{,\kappa}] - g^{\kappa\lambda}(g_{\mu\nu}\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma}\delta^{\rho}_{\nu})\Omega_{,\kappa}\Omega_{,\lambda}].
\end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{R}^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu} = & R^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu} + \underbrace{\delta^{\rho}_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu})_{,\sigma} - \delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu})_{,\nu}}_{(i)} - \underbrace{g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}(g_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma,\nu})}_{(ii)} \\
& + \underbrace{g_{\mu\sigma}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\sigma}}_{(iii)} \\
& + \Omega^{-1}[\underbrace{(\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\sigma})\Omega_{,\kappa}}_{(i)} - \underbrace{g^{\rho\lambda}(g_{\sigma\kappa}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu} - g_{\nu\kappa}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\sigma})\Omega_{,\lambda}}_{(ii)} \\
& - \underbrace{g^{\kappa\lambda}(g_{\mu\nu}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\sigma\kappa} - g_{\mu\sigma}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\nu\kappa})\Omega_{,\lambda}}_{(iii)}] + \Omega^{-2}[(\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\Omega_{,\nu} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\Omega_{,\sigma})\Omega_{,\mu} \\
& - g^{\rho\kappa}(g_{\mu\sigma}\Omega_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\sigma})\Omega_{,\kappa}] - g^{\kappa\lambda}(g_{\mu\nu}\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma}\delta^{\rho}_{\nu})\Omega_{,\kappa}\Omega_{,\lambda}]. \tag{11}
\end{aligned}$$

We must note the underbraced terms, where the terms underbraced with (i) result in,

$$\delta^{\rho}_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu})_{,\sigma} - \delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu})_{,\nu} + \Omega^{-1}(\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\sigma})\Omega_{,\kappa} = \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\nabla_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) - \delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\nabla_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}).$$

The terms underbraced with (ii) result in,

$$\begin{aligned}
& -g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}(g_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma,\nu}) - \Omega^{-1}g^{\rho\lambda}(g_{\sigma\kappa}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\nu} - g_{\nu\kappa}\Gamma^{\kappa}_{\mu\sigma})\Omega_{,\lambda} = \\
& g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}(g_{\mu\sigma,\nu} - g_{\sigma\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\mu\nu} - \underbrace{g_{\mu\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\sigma\nu} + g_{\mu\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\sigma\nu} - g_{\mu\nu,\sigma} + g_{\nu\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\mu\sigma}}_{\text{zero}}) = \\
& g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}[(g_{\mu\sigma,\nu} - g_{\sigma\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\mu\nu} - g_{\mu\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\sigma\nu}) - (g_{\mu\nu,\sigma} - g_{\nu\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\mu\sigma} - g_{\mu\lambda}\Gamma^{\lambda}_{\sigma\nu})] = \\
& g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}[\nabla_{\nu}g_{\mu\sigma} - \nabla_{\sigma}g_{\mu\nu}] = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

The terms underbraced with (iii) result in,

$$\begin{aligned}
& g_{\mu\sigma}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\sigma} - g^{\kappa\lambda}(g_{\mu\nu}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\sigma\kappa} - g_{\mu\sigma}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\nu\kappa})\Omega_{,\lambda} = \\
& g_{\mu\sigma}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\nu} + g_{\mu\sigma}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\nu\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}g^{\kappa\lambda}\Omega_{,\lambda}) - [g_{\mu\nu}(g^{\rho\kappa}\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})_{,\sigma} + g_{\mu\nu}\Gamma^{\rho}_{\sigma\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}g^{\kappa\lambda}\Omega_{,\lambda})] = \\
& g_{\mu\sigma}\nabla_{\nu}[g^{\rho\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})] - g_{\mu\nu}\nabla_{\sigma}[g^{\rho\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})] = g_{\mu\sigma}g^{\rho\kappa}\nabla_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) - g_{\mu\nu}g^{\rho\kappa}\nabla_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}).
\end{aligned}$$

With the three results above and going back into the equation (11), we can rewrite it as,

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{R}^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu} = & R^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu} + \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}\nabla_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) - \delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}\nabla_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) + g_{\mu\sigma}g^{\rho\kappa}\nabla_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) \\
& - g_{\mu\nu}g^{\rho\kappa}\nabla_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + \delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\nu})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\sigma})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) \\
& - g^{\rho\kappa}g_{\mu\sigma}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\nu})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + g^{\rho\kappa}g_{\mu\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\sigma})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + (g_{\mu\sigma}\delta^{\rho}_{\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}\delta^{\rho}_{\sigma})g^{\kappa\lambda}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\lambda}).
\end{aligned}$$

We can separate the above terms into groups with four square brackets

$$\bar{R}^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu} = R^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + g_{\mu\sigma}[g^{\rho\kappa}\nabla_\nu(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) - g^{\rho\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\nu})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + \frac{1}{2}\delta^\rho_\nu g^{\kappa\lambda}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\lambda})] \\
& - g_{\mu\nu}[g^{\rho\kappa}\nabla_\sigma(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) - g^{\rho\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\sigma})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + \frac{1}{2}\delta^\rho_\sigma g^{\kappa\lambda}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\lambda})] \\
& + \delta^\rho_\nu g_{\mu\tau}[g^{\tau\kappa}\nabla_\sigma(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) - g^{\tau\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\sigma})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + \frac{1}{2}\delta^\tau_\sigma g^{\kappa\lambda}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\lambda})] \\
& - \delta^\rho_\sigma g_{\mu\tau}[g^{\tau\kappa}\nabla_\nu(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) - g^{\tau\kappa}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\nu})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa}) + \frac{1}{2}\delta^\tau_\nu g^{\kappa\lambda}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\lambda})].
\end{aligned}$$

Bracketed terms form tensors that can simplify the Riemann tensor,

$$\bar{R}^\rho_{\mu\sigma\nu} = R^\rho_{\mu\sigma\nu} + g_{\mu\sigma}B_\nu{}^\rho - g_{\mu\nu}B_\sigma{}^\rho + \delta^\rho_\nu g_{\mu\tau}B_\sigma{}^\tau - \delta^\rho_\sigma g_{\mu\tau}B_\nu{}^\tau, \quad (12)$$

where we can define

$$B_\kappa{}^\lambda = g^{\lambda\mu}\nabla_\kappa(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) - g^{\lambda\mu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\kappa})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) + \frac{1}{2}\delta^\lambda_\kappa g^{\mu\nu}(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu})(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\nu}).$$

We can calculate the covariant derivative in the above equation,

$$\nabla_\kappa(\Omega^{-1}\Omega_{,\mu}) = -\Omega^{-2}\Omega_{,\kappa}\Omega_{,\mu} + \Omega^{-1}\Omega_{;\kappa\mu},$$

where we use the shorthand semicolon notation $\Omega_{;\kappa\mu} = \nabla_\kappa\Omega_{,\mu}$. So, we have,

$$B_\kappa{}^\lambda = \Omega^{-1}g^{\lambda\mu}\Omega_{;\kappa\mu} - 2\Omega^{-2}g^{\lambda\mu}\Omega_{,\kappa}\Omega_{,\mu} + \frac{1}{2}\Omega^{-2}\delta^\lambda_\kappa g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\mu}\Omega_{,\nu},$$

or with the two covariant indices,

$$B_{\kappa\lambda} = \Omega^{-1}\Omega_{;\kappa\lambda} - 2\Omega^{-2}\Omega_{,\kappa}\Omega_{,\lambda} + \frac{1}{2}g_{\kappa\lambda}g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\mu}\Omega_{,\nu},$$

The trace of the above tensor is obtained by

$$B_\kappa{}^\kappa = \Omega^{-1}g^{\kappa\mu}\Omega_{;\kappa\mu} - 2\Omega^{-2}g^{\kappa\mu}\Omega_{,\kappa}\Omega_{,\mu} + \frac{1}{2}\Omega^{-2}\delta^\kappa_\kappa g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\mu}\Omega_{,\nu}.$$

being that $\delta^\kappa_\kappa = m$ where m is the dimension of manifold. The trace is

$$B_\kappa{}^\kappa = \Omega^{-1}g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{;\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{m-4}{2}\right)\Omega^{-2}g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\mu}\Omega_{,\nu}. \quad (13)$$

When calculating the Ricci tensor from the equation (12) we can obtain

$$\bar{R}_{\mu\nu} = \bar{R}^\sigma_{\mu\sigma\nu} = R^\sigma_{\mu\sigma\nu} + g_{\mu\sigma}B_\nu{}^\sigma - g_{\mu\nu}B_\sigma{}^\sigma + \delta^\sigma_\nu B_{\sigma\mu} - \delta^\sigma_\sigma B_{\nu\mu},$$

or

$$\bar{R}_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}B_\sigma{}^\sigma - (m-2)B_{\mu\nu}. \quad (14)$$

To obtain the curvature scalar it passes through the calculus,

$$\bar{g}^{\kappa\mu}\bar{R}_{\mu\nu} = \Omega^{-2}\left(g^{\kappa\mu}R_{\mu\nu} - \delta^\kappa_\mu B_\nu{}^\sigma - (m-2)g^{\kappa\mu}B_{\mu\nu}\right),$$

that results in

$$\bar{R}^\kappa{}_\nu = \Omega^{-2}\left(g^{\kappa\mu}R_{\mu\nu} - \delta^\kappa_\nu B_\sigma{}^\sigma - (m-2)B_\nu{}^\kappa\right),$$

then the curvature scalar results in

$$\bar{R} = \bar{R}^\kappa{}_\kappa = \Omega^{-2}\left(g^{\kappa\mu}R_{\mu\kappa} - \delta^\kappa_\kappa B_\sigma{}^\sigma - (m-2)B_\kappa{}^\kappa\right)$$

or

$$\bar{R} = \Omega^{-2}\left[R - 2(m-1)B_\kappa{}^\kappa\right]. \quad (15)$$

Placing the result of tensor $B_\kappa{}^\kappa$ of the equation (13) into above equation (15) we can obtain,

$$\bar{R} = \Omega^{-2}\left\{R - 2(m-1)\left[\Omega^{-1}g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{;\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{m-4}{2}\right)\Omega^{-2}g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\mu}\Omega_{,\nu}\right]\right\},$$

which can be simplified to

$$\bar{R} = \Omega^{-2}R - 2(m-1)\Omega^{-3}g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{;\mu\nu} - (m-1)(m-4)\Omega^{-4}g^{\mu\nu}\Omega_{,\mu}\Omega_{,\nu}. \quad (16)$$

3. The Weyl curvature tensor

The goal now is to calculate the Weyl curvature tensor. For that let us go back to the equation (12),

$$\bar{R}^\rho{}_{\mu\sigma\nu} = R^\rho{}_{\mu\sigma\nu} + g_{\mu\sigma}B_{\nu}{}^\rho - g_{\mu\nu}B_{\sigma}{}^\rho + \delta^\rho{}_\nu B_{\sigma\mu} - \delta^\rho{}_\sigma B_{\nu\mu}.$$

From equation (15) we have

$$\bar{R} = \Omega^{-2} [R - 2(m-1)B_{\kappa}{}^\kappa]$$

such that

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R} &= (\Omega^2 g_{\mu\nu})\Omega^{-2} [R - 2(m-1)B_{\kappa}{}^\kappa] \\ \bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R} &= g_{\mu\nu}R - 2(m-1)g_{\mu\nu}B_{\kappa}{}^\kappa,\end{aligned}$$

so putting in evidence the term of trace of tensor $B_{\mu\nu}$, we have that,

$$g_{\mu\nu}B_{\kappa}{}^\kappa = \frac{g_{\mu\nu}R - \bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R}}{2(m-1)}.$$

Now we must replace the result above in the equation (14),

$$\bar{R}_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}B_{\kappa}{}^\kappa - (m-2)B_{\mu\nu},$$

to get the following result

$$\bar{R}_{\mu\nu} - R_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R} - g_{\mu\nu}R}{2(m-1)} - (m-2)B_{\mu\nu},$$

thus we have that the tensor $B_{\mu\nu}$ is

$$B_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R} - g_{\mu\nu}R}{2(m-2)(m-1)} + \frac{R_{\mu\nu} - \bar{R}_{\mu\nu}}{m-2}. \quad (17)$$

The next step is to write the Riemann tensor (12) with all indexes down as follows way,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{g}_{\kappa\rho}\bar{R}^\rho{}_{\mu\sigma\nu} = \bar{R}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} &= \Omega^2 g_{\kappa\rho}(R^\rho{}_{\mu\sigma\nu} + g_{\mu\sigma}B_{\nu}{}^\rho - g_{\mu\nu}B_{\sigma}{}^\rho + \delta^\rho{}_\nu B_{\sigma\mu} - \delta^\rho{}_\sigma B_{\nu\mu}) \\ \bar{R}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} &= \Omega^2 (R_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + g_{\mu\sigma}B_{\nu\kappa} - g_{\mu\nu}B_{\sigma\kappa} + g_{\kappa\nu}B_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\kappa\sigma}B_{\nu\mu}),\end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

and replace the equation (17) into equation above (18), such that,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{R}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} = \Omega^2 \left[R_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + g_{\mu\sigma} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\kappa\nu}\bar{R} - g_{\kappa\nu}R}{2(m-2)(m-1)} + \frac{R_{\kappa\nu} - \bar{R}_{\kappa\nu}}{m-2} \right) - g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{R} - g_{\kappa\sigma}R}{2(m-2)(m-1)} + \frac{R_{\kappa\sigma} - \bar{R}_{\kappa\sigma}}{m-2} \right) \right. \\ \left. + g_{\kappa\nu} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma}\bar{R} - g_{\mu\sigma}R}{2(m-2)(m-1)} + \frac{R_{\mu\sigma} - \bar{R}_{\mu\sigma}}{m-2} \right) - g_{\kappa\sigma} \left(\frac{\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R} - g_{\mu\nu}R}{2(m-2)(m-1)} + \frac{R_{\mu\nu} - \bar{R}_{\mu\nu}}{m-2} \right) \right]. \quad (19)\end{aligned}$$

Separating the Ricci tensors terms from the curvature scalar and also grouping the barred terms of the non-barred, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega^{-2}\bar{R}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} &= R_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\mu\sigma}R_{\kappa\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}R_{\kappa\sigma} + g_{\kappa\nu}R_{\mu\sigma} - g_{\kappa\sigma}R_{\mu\nu}) \\ &+ \frac{R}{2(m-2)(m-1)}(-g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\kappa\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}g_{\kappa\sigma} - g_{\kappa\nu}g_{\mu\sigma} + g_{\kappa\sigma}g_{\mu\nu}) \\ &+ \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\mu\sigma}\bar{R}_{\kappa\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}\bar{R}_{\kappa\sigma} + g_{\kappa\nu}\bar{R}_{\mu\sigma} - g_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{R}_{\mu\nu}) \\ &+ \frac{\bar{R}}{2(m-2)(m-1)}(-g_{\mu\sigma}\bar{g}_{\kappa\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}\bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma} - g_{\kappa\nu}\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma} + g_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}).\end{aligned}$$

Now we must separate the barred and non-barred terms,

$$\Omega^{-2}\bar{R}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\mu\sigma}\bar{R}_{\kappa\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}\bar{R}_{\kappa\sigma} + g_{\kappa\nu}\bar{R}_{\mu\sigma} - g_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{R}_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{\bar{R}}{2(m-2)(m-1)}(-g_{\mu\sigma}\bar{g}_{\kappa\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}\bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma} - g_{\kappa\nu}\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma} + g_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{g}_{\mu\nu})$$

$$= R_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\mu\sigma}R_{\kappa\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}R_{\kappa\sigma} + g_{\kappa\nu}R_{\mu\sigma} - g_{\kappa\sigma}R_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}(g_{\mu\nu}g_{\kappa\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\kappa\nu}).$$

Recall the local rescaling metric of the metric tensor from equation (6), where we have $g_{\mu\nu} = \Omega^{-2}\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}$, so that,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega^{-2}\bar{R}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} &+ \frac{\Omega^{-2}}{m-2}(\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma}\bar{R}_{\kappa\nu} - \bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R}_{\kappa\sigma} + \bar{g}_{\kappa\nu}\bar{R}_{\mu\sigma} - \bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{R}_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{\bar{R}\Omega^{-2}}{2(m-2)(m-1)}(-\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma}\bar{g}_{\kappa\nu} + \bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma} - \bar{g}_{\kappa\nu}\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma} + \bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}) \\ &= R_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\mu\sigma}R_{\kappa\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}R_{\kappa\sigma} + g_{\kappa\nu}R_{\mu\sigma} - g_{\kappa\sigma}R_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}(g_{\mu\nu}g_{\kappa\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\kappa\nu}), \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega^{-2}\left[\bar{R}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(\bar{g}_{\mu\sigma}\bar{R}_{\kappa\nu} - \bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{R}_{\kappa\sigma} + \bar{g}_{\kappa\nu}\bar{R}_{\mu\sigma} - \bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma}\bar{R}_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{\bar{R}}{(m-2)(m-1)}(\bar{g}_{\mu\nu}\bar{g}_{\kappa\sigma} - \bar{g}_{\mu\sigma}\bar{g}_{\kappa\nu})\right] \\ = R_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\mu\sigma}R_{\kappa\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}R_{\kappa\sigma} + g_{\kappa\nu}R_{\mu\sigma} - g_{\kappa\sigma}R_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}(g_{\mu\nu}g_{\kappa\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\kappa\nu}). \end{aligned}$$

unless of the factor Ω^{-2} , algebraically the left side is equal to the right side. Thus we can write the equation above in a compact format,

$$\Omega^{-2}\bar{C}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} = C_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu}, \quad (20)$$

where the tensor $C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$ is called Weyl curvature tensor given by,

$$C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = R_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\lambda\mu}R_{\kappa\nu} - g_{\lambda\nu}R_{\kappa\mu} + g_{\kappa\nu}R_{\lambda\mu} - g_{\kappa\mu}R_{\lambda\nu}) + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}(g_{\lambda\nu}g_{\kappa\mu} - g_{\lambda\mu}g_{\kappa\nu}), \quad (21)$$

or in terms of antisymmetrization of index pair by square brackets we have,

$$C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = R_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + \frac{2}{m-2}(g_{\kappa[\nu}R_{\mu]\lambda} + g_{\lambda[\mu}R_{\nu]\kappa}) + \frac{2R}{(m-2)(m-1)}g_{\kappa[\mu}g_{\nu]\lambda}. \quad (22)$$

In the equation (20) we can apply $g^{k\rho}$ so that we have

$$\begin{aligned} g^{k\rho}\Omega^{-2}\bar{C}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} &= g^{k\rho}C_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu}, \\ \bar{g}^{k\rho}\bar{C}_{\kappa\mu\sigma\nu} &= C^{\rho}_{\mu\sigma\nu}, \end{aligned}$$

therefore, we have

$$\bar{C}^{\kappa}_{\lambda\mu\nu} = C^{\kappa}_{\lambda\mu\nu}, \quad (23)$$

consequently the Weyl tensor has the special property that it is invariant under conformal changes to the metric (2), and for this reason the Weyl tensor is also called the conformal tensor.

Let us calculate the trace of Weyl curvature tensor given by, $C_{\mu\nu} = C^{\kappa}_{\mu\kappa\nu}$. For that, let us go back to the equation (21) as follows,

$$C^{\kappa}_{\mu\kappa\nu} = R^{\kappa}_{\mu\kappa\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\mu\kappa}R_{\nu}^{\kappa} - g_{\mu\nu}R_{\kappa}^{\kappa} + \delta^{\kappa}_{\nu}R_{\mu\kappa} - \delta^{\kappa}_{\kappa}R_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}(g_{\mu\nu}\delta^{\kappa}_{\kappa} - \delta^{\mu}_{\kappa}g_{\nu\kappa}),$$

this equation above results in

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\mu\nu} &= R_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(R_{\mu\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}R + R_{\mu\nu} - mR_{\mu\nu}) + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}(mg_{\mu\nu} - g_{\mu\nu}) \\ C_{\mu\nu} &= R_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}[R_{\mu\nu}(-m+2) - g_{\mu\nu}R] + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}((m-1)g_{\mu\nu}) \\ C_{\mu\nu} &= R_{\mu\nu} - R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{g_{\mu\nu}R}{m-2} + \frac{g_{\mu\nu}R}{m-2} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The Weyl curvature tensor is completely traceless.

If every point of a spacetime (\mathcal{M}, \bar{g}) , the metric tensor is $\bar{g}_{\mu\nu} = \Omega^2\eta_{\mu\nu}$, where $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of flat Minkowski spacetime, then (\mathcal{M}, \bar{g}) is said to be conformally flat. Since the Wey tensor for a flat Minkowski metric is null, it is also null for a conformally flat metric.

4. Decomposition of the Riemann curvature tensor

It is possible to express the curvature Riemann tensor in terms of Weyl curvature tensor, Ricci tensor and scalar of curvature, when we isolate the Riemann curvature tensor in the equation we have (21),

$$R_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = C_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{m-2}(g_{\sigma\nu}R_{\rho\mu} + g_{\rho\mu}R_{\sigma\nu} - g_{\sigma\mu}R_{\rho\nu} - g_{\rho\nu}R_{\sigma\mu}) + \frac{R}{(m-2)(m-1)}(g_{\rho\nu}g_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\rho\mu}g_{\sigma\nu}). \quad (25)$$

Let us consider the 4-dimensional space V^4 , where we must have $m = 4$ in above equation, such as,

$$R_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = C_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2}(g_{\sigma\nu}R_{\rho\mu} + g_{\rho\mu}R_{\sigma\nu} - g_{\sigma\mu}R_{\rho\nu} - g_{\rho\nu}R_{\sigma\mu}) + \frac{R}{6}(g_{\rho\nu}g_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\rho\mu}g_{\sigma\nu}). \quad (26)$$

It is common to use the definition below

$$E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2}(g_{\rho\mu}S_{\sigma\nu} + g_{\sigma\nu}S_{\rho\mu} - g_{\rho\nu}S_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\sigma\mu}S_{\rho\nu}), \quad (27)$$

where $S_{\rho\sigma}$ is a traceless part of the Ricci tensor, the reduced Ricci tensor given by

$$S_{\rho\sigma} = R_{\rho\sigma} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\rho\sigma}R \quad (28)$$

so that

$$g^{\rho\sigma}S_{\rho\sigma} = 0. \quad (29)$$

We can also identify the reduced Ricci tensor with the the Einstein tensor,

$$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R, \quad (30)$$

with the trace $G_{\mu}^{\mu} = G = -R$, we have that

$$S_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}G. \quad (31)$$

Notice that the tensor $E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu}$ is expressed as

$$E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2}[(g_{\rho\mu}R_{\sigma\nu} + g_{\sigma\nu}R_{\rho\mu} - g_{\rho\nu}R_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\sigma\mu}R_{\rho\nu}) - \frac{1}{8}(g_{\rho\mu}g_{\sigma\nu} + g_{\sigma\nu}g_{\rho\mu} - g_{\rho\nu}g_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\sigma\mu}g_{\rho\nu})R], \quad (32)$$

or then,

$$E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2}(g_{\rho\mu}R_{\sigma\nu} + g_{\sigma\nu}R_{\rho\mu} - g_{\rho\nu}R_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\sigma\mu}R_{\rho\nu}) + \frac{R}{4}(g_{\rho\nu}g_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\rho\mu}g_{\sigma\nu}). \quad (33)$$

Note that the first term of the equation above is equal to the second term of the equation (26), but that the second term of the expression above has a factor $\frac{R}{4}$ and the equation (26) has a factor $\frac{R}{6}$. In this way we express the Riemann curvature tensor as follows

$$R_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = C_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} + E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} - \frac{R}{12}(g_{\rho\nu}g_{\sigma\mu} - g_{\rho\mu}g_{\sigma\nu}),$$

or then,

$$R_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = C_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} + E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} + \frac{R}{12}(g_{\rho\mu}g_{\sigma\nu} - g_{\rho\nu}g_{\sigma\mu}),$$

where we can define the new tensor,

$$G_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = \frac{R}{12}(g_{\rho\mu}g_{\sigma\nu} - g_{\rho\nu}g_{\sigma\mu}). \quad (34)$$

Thus we come to the Riemann curvature tensor in a 4-dimensional Riemann space V^4 ,

$$R_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} = C_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} + E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu} + G_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu}. \quad (35)$$

We must calculate the trace of the tensor $G_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu}$, as follows as

$$G^{\rho}_{\sigma\rho\nu} = \frac{R}{12}(\delta^{\rho}_{\rho}g_{\sigma\nu} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}g_{\sigma\rho}) = \frac{R}{12}(4g_{\sigma\nu} - g_{\sigma\nu}) = \frac{R}{4}g_{\sigma\nu}, \quad (36)$$

and from equation (27), the calculation of the trace of the tensor $E_{\rho\sigma\mu\nu}$ is given by,

$$E^{\rho}_{\sigma\rho\nu} = \frac{1}{2}(\delta^{\rho}_{\rho}S_{\sigma\nu} + g_{\sigma\nu}S^{\rho}_{\rho} - \delta^{\rho}_{\nu}S_{\sigma\rho} - \delta^{\rho}_{\sigma}S_{\rho\nu}) = \frac{1}{2}(4S_{\sigma\nu} - 0 - S_{\sigma\nu} - S_{\sigma\nu}) = S_{\sigma\nu}. \quad (37)$$

With this it can be confirmed that the trace of the Riemann curvature tensor, given by:

$$R^{\rho}_{\sigma\rho\nu} = C^{\rho}_{\sigma\rho\nu} + E^{\rho}_{\sigma\rho\nu} + G^{\rho}_{\sigma\rho\nu},$$

results in the Ricci tensor,

$$R^{\rho}_{\sigma\rho\nu} = 0 + S_{\sigma\nu} + \frac{R}{4}g_{\sigma\nu} = R_{\sigma\nu} - \frac{R}{4}g_{\sigma\nu} + \frac{R}{4}g_{\sigma\nu} = R_{\sigma\nu}.$$

We know that the full Riemann curvature tensor has 20 independent components [2, 3, 12, 13, 14, 15] whereas the Ricci tensor has 10 independent components because it is symmetric tensor, $R_{\mu\nu} = R_{\nu\mu}$, then we can take a look again at the equation (26) and to observe that the Weyl curvature tensor must have the other 10 independent components which at any point are completely independent of the Ricci tensor components.

The Riemann curvature tensor is a sum of the Weyl curvature tensor plus terms built out of the Ricci tensor and scalar curvature, then for vacuum solutions such as Schwarzschild and Kerr spacetimes, we have $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and $R = 0$, and consequently the Weyl curvature tensor is exactly the same Riemann curvature tensors. We say, therefore, that the curvature Weyl tensor corresponds to the free gravitational field [16].

In basic courses of General Relativity we have studied the equation of geodesic variation [12, 13, 14, 15] that measures convergence or divergence of two nearby geodesics initially parallel in a curved spacetime, depending on the local curvature $R^{\mu}_{\nu\rho\sigma}$. If we consider an initial spherical distribution of non-interacting particles freely falling towards the Earth, each particle moves on a straight line through the centre of the Earth. The particles more near the Earth fall faster because the gravitational attraction is stronger. Then the spherical distribution of particles no longer remains a sphere shape but is distorted into an ellipsoid of the same volume. Thus the gravity has produced a tidal force in the sphere of particles that results in an elongation of the distribution in the direction of motion and a compression of the distribution in the transverse direction. Let us consider any pair of non-interaction particles in a sphere of particles, each one is in free fall and so they must move along the timelike geodesics $x^{\mu}(\tau)$ and $y^{\mu}(\tau)$ respectively, where τ is the proper time experienced by the first particle. We can define a small separation vector between the two particle worldlines by $\xi^{\mu}(\tau) = y^{\mu}(\tau) - x^{\mu}(\tau)$, then we have that the tidal forces of a gravitational field is given by,

$$\frac{d^2\xi^{\mu}}{d\tau^2} = R^{\mu}_{\rho\sigma\nu}u^{\rho}u^{\sigma}\xi^{\nu}, \quad (38)$$

where $u^{\rho} = \frac{dx^{\rho}}{d\tau}$. The tidal forces can be represented by curvature of a spacetime in which particles follow geodesics. Therefore if we consider a spherical distribution of particles in vacuum space nearby to gravitating astrophysical spherical body, where the spacetime is Schwarzschild or Kerr spacetime, we have that $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ and $R = 0$ and from equation (26), we have that the Riemann curvature tensor becomes $R^{\mu}_{\nu\rho\sigma} = C^{\mu}_{\nu\rho\sigma}$ and the equation (38) for tidal forces of a free gravitational field reads,

$$\frac{d^2\xi^{\mu}}{d\tau^2} = C^{\mu}_{\rho\sigma\nu}u^{\rho}u^{\sigma}\xi^{\nu}. \quad (39)$$

The Weyl tensor expresses the tidal force that a body feels when moving along a geodesic.

When we consider a general gravitational perturbation $h_{\mu\nu}$ satisfying the empty-space linearised field equation and the Lorentz gauge condition, among some solutions there are plane-wave solutions in vacuum space [12, 13, 14, 15]. If we consider the famous circular ring of test particles in the transverse plane to propagation of the plane-wave in vacuum space, surrounding a central particle, we can verify that the wave deforms what was a ring as measured in the proper reference frame of the central particle into an ellipse, causing the ring to oscillate in various modes of

polarization. Because the linear plane-wave is in the vacuum the Ricci tensor and curvature scalar are nulls, the oscillating curvature tensor is the Weyl curvature tensor that produce the tidal acceleration between various particles in accordance with equation (39). Therefore the Weyl tensor is locally measurable by simply watching the proper distance changes between nearby geodesics. The Weyl curvature is the only part of the curvature that exists in free gravitational field and it governs the propagation of gravitational waves through regions of space devoid of matter.

5. Ruse-Lanczos Identity

Let us consider at a point p in the manifold \mathcal{M} those tensors \mathbf{W} of type $(0, 4)$ satisfying the algebraic symmetries similar to the Riemann curvature tensor,

$$W_{\lambda\kappa\mu\nu} = -W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = -W_{\lambda\kappa\nu\mu}, \quad W_{\lambda\kappa\mu\nu} = W_{\mu\nu\lambda\kappa} \quad (40)$$

and

$$W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + W_{\kappa\mu\lambda\nu} + W_{\kappa\nu\lambda\mu} = 0. \quad (41)$$

Tensors with the properties defined above, such as the curvature tensor, with two pairs of antisymmetric indices, there is a definition of two duality operations [4, 17, 18], the left dual $\sim W$ and right dual $W\sim$ defined by,

$$\sim W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = W_{\tau\phi\mu\nu} g^{\rho\tau} g^{\sigma\phi} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} W^{\rho\sigma}{}_{\mu\nu} \quad (42)$$

and

$$W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}\sim = W_{\kappa\lambda\tau\phi} g^{\rho\tau} g^{\sigma\phi} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} = W_{\kappa\lambda}{}^{\rho\sigma} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}. \quad (43)$$

As a consequence of double application of the left duality operation one have,

$$\sim\sim W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} \sim W^{\rho\sigma}{}_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon^{\rho\sigma\tau\phi} W_{\tau\phi\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4} (-2) (\delta_{\kappa}{}^{\tau} \delta_{\lambda}{}^{\phi} - \delta_{\kappa}{}^{\phi} \delta_{\lambda}{}^{\tau}) W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = -\frac{1}{2} (W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} - W_{\lambda\kappa\mu\nu}),$$

with aid of equation (40), where one have $W_{\lambda\kappa\mu\nu} = -W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$, it follows as,

$$\sim\sim W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = -W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}. \quad (44)$$

The double application of the right duality operation is similar to double left duality operation, where one have,

$$W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}\sim\sim = -W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}. \quad (45)$$

In order to obtain the Ruse-Lanczos identity [4], we need to calculate left and right duality simultaneously as we will perform,

$$\sim W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}\sim = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} \left(W^{\rho\sigma\tau\phi} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\tau\phi} \right),$$

it can be rearranged as follows,

$$\sim W^{\sim\kappa\lambda}{}_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4} \epsilon^{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\tau\phi} W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi}. \quad (46)$$

Let us pause here to calculate

$$\epsilon^{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\tau\phi} = -\delta^{\kappa}{}_{\mu} \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\nu} \delta^{\rho}{}_{\tau} \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\phi} = - \begin{vmatrix} \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\rho}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\phi} \end{vmatrix}$$

or

$$-\epsilon^{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\tau\phi} = \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\mu} \begin{vmatrix} \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\rho}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\phi} \end{vmatrix} - \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\nu} \begin{vmatrix} \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\rho}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\tau} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\phi} \end{vmatrix} + \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\tau} \begin{vmatrix} \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\rho}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\phi} \\ \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\phi} \end{vmatrix} - \delta^{\kappa}{}_{\phi} \begin{vmatrix} \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\lambda}{}_{\tau} \\ \delta^{\rho}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\rho}{}_{\tau} \\ \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\mu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\nu} & \delta^{\sigma}{}_{\tau} \end{vmatrix}$$

with more details we have

$$\begin{aligned}
-\epsilon^{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma}\epsilon_{\mu\nu\tau\phi} &= \delta^\kappa_\mu \left(\delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\phi + \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\nu + \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\tau - \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\nu - \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\phi - \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\tau \right) \\
&\quad - \delta^\kappa_\nu \left(\delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\phi + \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\mu + \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\tau - \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\mu - \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\phi - \delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\tau \right) \\
&\quad + \delta^\kappa_\tau \left(\delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\phi + \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\mu + \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\nu - \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\mu - \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\phi - \delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\nu \right) \\
&\quad - \delta^\kappa_\phi \left(\delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\tau + \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\mu + \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\nu - \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\mu - \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\tau - \delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\nu \right)
\end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Now we must look at the equation (46), where we have $\tilde{W}^{\sim\kappa\lambda}{}_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{4}\epsilon^{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma}\epsilon_{\mu\nu\tau\phi}W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi}$, we are going to multiply the tensor $W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi}$ with each above parentheses. The the first calculation is

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta^\kappa_\mu \left(\delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\phi + \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\nu + \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\tau - \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\nu - \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\phi - \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\tau \right) W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi} \\
= 2\delta^\kappa_\mu \left(\delta^\lambda_\nu W_{\tau\phi}{}^{\tau\phi} + W_{\tau\nu}{}^{\lambda\tau} + W_{\nu\tau}{}^{\tau\lambda} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Recalling that the tensor W is similar to algebraic symmetries of Riemann curvature tensor, we have from equation (40) that $W_{\nu\tau}{}^{\tau\lambda} = W_{\tau\nu}{}^{\lambda\tau}$ and also $W^{\tau}{}_{\nu\tau\lambda} = W_{\nu\lambda}$ and besides that $W_{\tau\phi}{}^{\tau\phi} = W^{\tau\phi}{}_{\tau\phi} = W^\phi{}_\phi = W$. Thus we have that,

$$\delta^\kappa_\mu \left(\delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\phi + \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\nu + \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\tau - \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\nu - \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\phi - \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\tau \right) W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi} = 2\delta^\kappa_\mu \delta^\lambda_\nu W - 4\delta^\kappa_\mu W_\nu{}^\lambda. \quad (48)$$

The second parentheses of equation (47) multiplied by $W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi}$ results in,

$$\delta^\kappa_\nu \left(\delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\phi + \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\mu + \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\tau - \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\mu - \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\phi - \delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\tau \right) W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi} = 2\delta^\kappa_\nu \delta^\lambda_\mu W - 4\delta^\kappa_\nu W_\mu{}^\lambda. \quad (49)$$

The third parentheses of equation (47) multiplied by $W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi}$ results in,

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta^\kappa_\tau \left(\delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\phi + \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\mu + \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\nu - \delta^\lambda_\phi \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\mu - \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\phi - \delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\phi \delta^\sigma_\nu \right) W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi} = \\
2\delta^\lambda_\mu W_\nu{}^\kappa - 2\delta^\lambda_\nu W_\mu{}^\kappa + 2W_{\mu\nu}{}^{\kappa\lambda}.
\end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

And finally the fourth parentheses of equation (47) multiplied by $W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi}$ results in,

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta^\kappa_\phi \left(\delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\tau + \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\mu + \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\nu - \delta^\lambda_\tau \delta^\rho_\nu \delta^\sigma_\mu - \delta^\lambda_\nu \delta^\rho_\mu \delta^\sigma_\tau - \delta^\lambda_\mu \delta^\rho_\tau \delta^\sigma_\nu \right) W_{\rho\sigma}{}^{\tau\phi} = \\
-2\delta^\lambda_\mu W_\nu{}^\kappa + 2\delta^\lambda_\nu W_\mu{}^\kappa - 2W_{\mu\nu}{}^{\kappa\lambda}.
\end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Turning these results (48), (49), (50) and (51) back into the equation (47) we have,

$$-\epsilon^{\kappa\lambda\rho\sigma}\epsilon_{\mu\nu\tau\phi} = 2(\delta^\kappa_\mu \delta^\lambda_\nu - \delta^\kappa_\nu \delta^\lambda_\mu)W - 4(\delta^\kappa_\mu W_\nu{}^\lambda - \delta^\kappa_\nu W_\mu{}^\lambda - \delta^\lambda_\mu W_\nu{}^\kappa + \delta^\lambda_\nu W_\mu{}^\kappa) + 4W_{\mu\nu}{}^{\kappa\lambda} \quad (52)$$

Thus, we put the above equation (52) into equation (46) we have,

$$\tilde{W}^{\sim\kappa\lambda}{}_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{1}{4} \left[2(g_{\kappa\mu}g_{\lambda\nu} - g_{\kappa\nu}g_{\lambda\mu})W - 4(g_{\kappa\mu}W_{\lambda\nu} - g_{\kappa\nu}W_{\lambda\mu} - g_{\lambda\mu}W_{\kappa\nu} + g_{\lambda\nu}W_{\kappa\mu}) + 4W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} \right] \quad (53)$$

or

$$\tilde{W}^{\sim\kappa\lambda}{}_{\mu\nu} + W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = g_{\lambda\nu} \left(W_{\kappa\mu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\kappa\mu}W \right) - g_{\lambda\mu} \left(W_{\kappa\nu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\kappa\nu}W \right) + g_{\kappa\mu} \left(W_{\lambda\nu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\lambda\nu}W \right) - g_{\kappa\nu} \left(W_{\lambda\mu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\lambda\mu}W \right). \quad (54)$$

The above equation is Ruse-Lanczos identity. We can simplify the above equation by definition,

$$P_{\kappa\mu} = W_{\kappa\mu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\kappa\mu}W, \quad (55)$$

so that we have

$$\tilde{W}^{\sim\kappa\lambda}{}_{\mu\nu} + W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = g_{\kappa\mu}P_{\lambda\nu} - g_{\kappa\nu}P_{\lambda\mu} + g_{\lambda\nu}P_{\kappa\mu} - g_{\lambda\mu}P_{\kappa\nu}, \quad (56)$$

or

$$\tilde{W}^{\sim\kappa\lambda}{}_{\mu\nu} + W_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = g_{\kappa[\mu}P_{\nu]\lambda} + g_{\lambda[\nu}P_{\mu]\kappa}. \quad (57)$$

The Ruse-Lanczos identity can be applied to Riemann curvature tensor and its components, conformal Weyl tensor $C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$ as well as the others tensors $E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$ and $G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$ seen in equation (35).

6. Duality and complex formalism of the components of curvature tensor

The Riemann curvature tensor obeys the Ruse-Lanczos identity as follows in accordance with the equation (56), where for Riemann curvature tensor we can recall the definition (28), $S_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}R$, such as $P_{\mu\nu} \longrightarrow S_{\mu\nu}$, we have,

$$\tilde{R}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + R_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = g_{\kappa\mu}S_{\lambda\nu} - g_{\kappa\nu}S_{\lambda\mu} + g_{\lambda\nu}S_{\kappa\mu} - g_{\lambda\mu}S_{\kappa\nu}.$$

Then we can recall the equation (27), where we have $E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2}(g_{\kappa\mu}S_{\lambda\nu} + g_{\lambda\nu}S_{\kappa\mu} - g_{\kappa\nu}S_{\lambda\mu} - g_{\lambda\mu}S_{\kappa\nu})$, so that the above equation becomes,

$$\tilde{R}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + R_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = 2E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}. \quad (58)$$

Let us calculate the trace of the above equation with aid of the equation (37), where $E^{\mu}{}_{\lambda\mu\nu} = S_{\lambda\nu}$ and denoting $g^{\kappa\mu}\tilde{R}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} = \tilde{R}_{\lambda\nu}^{\sim}$ we have that,

$$\tilde{R}_{\lambda\nu}^{\sim} + R_{\lambda\nu} = 2S_{\lambda\nu} = 2\left(R_{\lambda\nu} - \frac{1}{4}g_{\lambda\nu}R\right),$$

that results in,

$$\tilde{R}_{\mu\nu}^{\sim} = G_{\mu\nu}, \quad (59)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor (30).

The first component of Riemann curvature tensor that we apply the Ruse-Lanczos identity is the Weyl curvature tensor, recalling the equation (24) where Weyl curvature tensor is completely traceless, such as $P_{\mu\nu} \longrightarrow C_{\mu\nu} = 0$ into equation (56) for Weyl tensor and we have,

$$\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (60)$$

The double application of the right duality operation into above equation we have,

$$\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim\sim} + C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} = 0,$$

with aid of equation (45) we have

$$\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} = C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim}. \quad (61)$$

The second component of Riemann curvature tensor that we apply the Ruse-Lanczos identity is the tensor $G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$ defined by equation (34), where it reads $G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = \frac{R}{12}(g_{\kappa\mu}g_{\lambda\nu} - g_{\kappa\nu}g_{\lambda\mu})$. For this tensor we have from equation (36), the trace of this tensor is $G^{\kappa}{}_{\mu\kappa\nu} = \frac{R}{4}g_{\mu\nu}$, such as the tensor $P_{\mu\nu}$ from definition (55) is null for tensor $G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$, that it results into Ruse-Lanczos identity (56) in the below equation,

$$\tilde{G}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (62)$$

and also the calculation performed for the above Weyl tensor, when we perform another right duality operation into above equation we have,

$$\tilde{G}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} = G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim}. \quad (63)$$

The third component of Riemann curvature tensor that we apply the Ruse-Lanczos identity is the tensor $E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$ defined by equation (27) to obtain the relation between the left dual and right dual. For this purpose we can return to equation (58) with the decomposition of Riemann curvature tensor obtained in the equation (35), where we have, $R_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}$, so that,

$$\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + \tilde{E}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + \tilde{G}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = 2E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu},$$

associating similar terms we have,

$$(\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}) + (\tilde{G}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}) + (\tilde{E}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} + E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}) = 2E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu},$$

with aid of the equation (60) and (62) the above equation is reduced to

$$\tilde{E}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} = E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu},$$

where another right duality operation into above equation results in,

$$\tilde{E}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = -E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} \quad (64)$$

For algebraic classification it is necessary to introduce the complex tensors

$$C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + iC_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} \quad (65)$$

$$E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = E_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + iE_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} \quad (66)$$

and

$$\mathcal{G}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = G_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + iG_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} \quad (67)$$

Applying left duality operation in the complex Weyl tensor in the equation (65) we obtain,

$$\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = \tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + i\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim}$$

here we can use the identities (61) and (60) so that the above equation produces

$$\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} - iC_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} = -i(C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} + iC_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim}),$$

or

$$\tilde{C}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = -iC_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* \quad (68)$$

The same procedure for the other two tensors (66) and (67) yield,

$$\tilde{E}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = iE_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* \quad (69)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* = -i\mathcal{G}_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* \quad (70)$$

The Weyl tensor in complex formalism seen in equation (65) was classified first by Petrov for characterization of the exact solutions of General Relativity [18, 19]. Just like the electromagnetic case, with aid of a timelike vector, four-velocity vector u^κ , where $u_\kappa u^\kappa = -1$, we can separate the ‘electric’ and ‘magnetic’ parts of the Weyl tensor,

$$C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^* u^\lambda u^\nu = C_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu} u^\lambda u^\nu + iC_{\kappa\lambda\mu\nu}^{\sim} u^\lambda u^\nu = E_{\kappa\mu} + iB_{\kappa\mu}. \quad (71)$$

In the bivector language the Weyl tensor is decomposed in five complex components and it is shown by means of the Petrov classification how the local free gravitational field is composed of the linear sum of the distinct components, a transverse wave, a longitudinal wave and a Coulomb component [16, 18, 19, 20].

7. Conclusion

The standard elements of the theory of General Relativity discussed in the basic literature [12, 13, 14, 15], it is superficially approached the details and the importance of the Weyl tensor. The purpose of this paper was to indicate details of calculations about obtaining the Weyl tensor from the conformal transformations. The duality and complexity properties of the Weyl tensor explored in books and articles dealing with advanced topics of General Relativity assume that students know the decomposition properties of the Riemann tensor and their duality properties, but often do not bridge the existing gap between the introductory and advanced levels. Then, from that point of knowledge of the duality and complexity properties of the Weyl tensor, it is possible to understand subsequent themes such as the Petrov classification and the Newman-Penrose equations for General Relativity.

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